

Parental decision-making for over-the-counter plant-based products used in children: A Bulgarian cross-sectional survey with implications for community pharmacy

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Abstract

Background: Over-the-counter (OTC) plant-based medicinal products are widely used in pediatric self-care, yet evidence on what drives parental product choice remains limited, particularly in Central and Eastern Europe. Understanding these decision drivers matters not only for counseling quality and safer self-medication but also for clarifying how community pharmacies function as real-world points of guidance in routine child self-care.

Aim: To identify the main determinants of parents' decisions when purchasing OTC plant-based products for children, with particular emphasis on the roles of physicians and pharmacists.

Methods: A cross-sectional anonymous online survey was conducted using Google Forms among parents in five Bulgarian cities (Sofia, Plovdiv, Ruse, Pazardzhik, and Dobrich) between December 2023 and April 2024. Descriptive statistics were calculated; associations were assessed using Pearson's chi-square test with Cramér's V, and multivariable logistic regression was applied for key decision factors.

Results: A total of 1305 respondents completed the questionnaire. Previous experience and physician recommendation were the strongest drivers of product choice. Pharmacist recommendation was also influential, with 64.0% of respondents rating it as moderately or very important; 92.5% reported purchasing these products from pharmacies, and 76.9% reported trusting pharmacists' advice. Advertising had the weakest influence (6.8% rated it as very important). Several apparent demographic differences attenuated after multivariable adjustment.

Conclusion: In this large Bulgarian convenience sample, parental decisions were shaped mainly by familiarity and professional advice rather than promotional messaging. The findings highlight community pharmacies as a practical setting for improved OTC counseling, safer pediatric self-care, and more evidence-aligned use of plant-based products, while also offering a useful country-specific reference point for future work on parental self-medication behavior in regulated pharmacy settings.

Graphical abstract

Parental decision-making for OTC plant-based products in children

Bulgaria | Cross-sectional survey

Keywords

Bulgaria, children, community pharmacy, counseling, herbal medicinal products, OTC medicines, parental decision-making, pediatric self-care, self-medication, survey

Introduction

Over-the-counter (OTC) plant-based medicinal products are widely used in pediatric self-care, yet relatively little is known about how parents weigh previous experience, professional advice, availability, price, and promotional cues when selecting these products for children. International evidence suggests that parent-directed medication choices are shaped by prior experience, perceived safety, convenience, symptom interpretation, and the credibility of professional advice rather than by any single factor alone (Seth et al. 2023; Tarcic et al. 2023; Aydin Aksoy et al. 2024; Haq et al. 2025). Country-specific analyses, therefore, remain important because the balance between self-care, physician input, pharmacist counseling, and retail access is influenced by the local OTC market, regulatory framework, and community-pharmacy culture.

In Bulgaria, recent work has documented both the substantial pediatric availability of plant-containing OTC medicines and the active role of community pharmacists in supporting more responsible self-medication (Hadzhieva and Petkova-Dimitrova 2024; Hadzhieva et al. 2025). Earlier Bulgarian work on OTC market practices likewise suggests that nonprescription product selection is shaped by more than product characteristics alone, which reinforces the relevance of market-facing

and point-of-purchase influences in this field (Petkova et al. 2014). The regulatory positioning of herbal medicinal products also deserves attention because parents may interpret plant origin as a marker of mildness or safety, even when age-related restrictions, indication boundaries, and evidence limitations still matter in practice (European Parliament and the Council 2004; Hadzhieva et al. 2023; European Medicines Agency 2023; European Medicines Agency 2024; European Medicines Agency 2025).

Evidence from neighboring and other international settings further suggests that parents may prefer plant-based options because they are viewed as familiar, natural, or gentler, while still turning to healthcare professionals when uncertainty or perceived risk increases (Seth et al. 2023; Petran et al. 2024; Haq et al. 2025). Against that background, the present study aimed to identify the main factors influencing parents' decisions when purchasing OTC plant-based products for children in Bulgaria, with particular emphasis on the relative roles of physicians, pharmacists, and non-professional influences. By clarifying which decision drivers matter most at the point of choice, the study provides practice-relevant evidence for community-pharmacy counseling and a useful comparative reference for future work on pediatric self-care, parental health behavior, and OTC decision-making in regulated pharmacy settings.

Materials and methods

Study design and setting

A cross-sectional survey design was employed. Data were collected using an anonymous online questionnaire administered via Google Forms between December 2023 and April 2024. The survey targeted parents residing in five Bulgarian cities: Sofia, Plovdiv, Ruse, Pazardzhik, and Dobrich.

Participants, sampling, and eligibility criteria

Participants were eligible if they were parents or legal guardians of at least one child aged 0–18 years, resided in one of the five target cities, and had previously purchased an OTC phytoproduct for their child. Participation was voluntary.

The survey link was shared through parenting-focused Facebook groups and Viber chats using a convenience sampling approach. Participants were not explicitly encouraged to forward the link to other eligible parents, and no incentives were offered. The resulting dataset therefore represents a large convenience sample rather than a probability-based representative sample.

Questionnaire development and reliability

The questionnaire included 25 items organized into five thematic sections: (1) demographic characteristics, (2) child-related variables, (3) frequency of OTC phytoproduct use, (4) sources of information, and (5) factors influencing product selection. The instrument was developed specifically for this study on the basis of a literature review and expert discussion.

No separate pilot survey was conducted. Internal consistency was therefore assessed in the final analytic sample. The seven decision-factor items presented in Table 2 showed acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.751; $N = 1305$). The three-item pharmacist-perception scale (accessibility, willingness to counsel, and trust) showed good internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = 0.854).

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics (v23.0). Descriptive statistics were calculated for all variables. Associations between categorical variables were assessed using chi-square tests (Pearson's chi-square), and effect sizes were estimated using Cramér's V . Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All chi-square analyses used complete cases ($N = 1305$). Decision-factor items (Table 2) used a 4-point importance scale (1–4) and were analyzed as ordinal categories. Purchase-channel and pharmacist-perception items used a 5-point agreement scale; for reporting, agreement was defined *a priori* as the two most positive options ('agree' and 'strongly agree'). In addition, multi-variable logistic regression models were fitted to estimate

adjusted associations between respondent characteristics (gender, age group, education, and city) and higher importance ratings (scores 3–4 vs. 1–2) for key decision factors (physician prescription, pharmacist recommendation, and previous experience). Age was categorized as ≤ 30 , 31–40, 41–50, and ≥ 51 years. Results are reported as adjusted odds ratios (aORs) with 95% confidence intervals.

Results

A total of 1305 completed questionnaires were analyzed. Most respondents were female (87.5%; $n = 1142$) and aged 30–39 years (47.6%; $n = 621$). The mean respondent age was 39.28 ± 6.66 years (mean \pm SD). The demographic characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Female	1142	87.5
Male	163	12.5
Age		
≤ 29 years	78	5.9
30–39 years	621	47.6
40–49 years	515	39.5
Over 50 years	91	7.0
Education		
Secondary	337	25.8
Secondary specialized	207	15.9
Professional bachelor's degree	41	3.1
Bachelor's degree	114	8.7
Master's degree	606	46.4
Child schooling stage in the household		
Nursery (approx. 0–3 years)	79	6.1
Kindergarten (approx. 3–6 years)	284	21.8
Primary school (grades 1–4)	275	21.1
Lower secondary (grades 5–7)	293	22.5
Upper secondary (grades 8–12)	594	45.5
Place of residence		
Sofia	39	3.0
Plovdiv	211	16.2
Ruse	625	47.9
Pazardzhik	368	28.2
Dobrich	62	4.8

Note: The 'Child schooling stage in the household' variable may exceed 100% because some respondents reported more than one child in different schooling stages. Schooling stage corresponds to typical age ranges in Bulgaria (nursery/kindergarten/primary/lower secondary/upper secondary).

Respondents from Ruse constituted nearly half of the sample (47.9%; $n = 625$), followed by Pazardzhik (28.2%; $n = 368$) and Plovdiv (16.2%; $n = 211$). Sofia (3.0%; $n = 39$) and Dobrich (4.8%; $n = 62$) contributed smaller proportions. These distributions reflect the dissemination channels and should be interpreted as a convenience sample rather than a representative population sample.

Respondents rated each decision factor on a 4-point scale (1 = not important at all, 2 = slightly important, 3 = moderately important, 4 = very important). Distributions are presented in Table 2.

Pharmacist recommendations were rated as moderately or very important by 64.0% of respondents, placing pharmacist input among the more influential determinants captured in the survey (Table 2).

Gender showed statistically significant associations with all seven decision factors, with small-to-moderate effect sizes (Cramér's *V* range 0.081–0.184; Table 3). Compared with men, women more often rated physician prescriptions and pharmacists' recommendations as important and were more likely to consider previous experience and perceived product quality, effectiveness, and safety as highly important. Advertising, price being unimportant, and proximity/availability also differed by gender, although effect sizes remained small.

Respondent age group was associated with physician-prescribed purchases, pharmacists' recommenda-

tions, purchasing based on previous experience, and perceived quality, effectiveness, and safety (all $p \leq 0.003$; Table 3). Associations with price being unimportant and advertising were weaker, and proximity/availability did not differ meaningfully by age group.

Education level was associated with physician-prescribed purchases and pharmacists' recommendations and showed the strongest bivariate relationships with purchasing based on previous experience and the influence of advertising (Table 3). Respondents with secondary education were more likely to rate advertising as important and less likely to emphasize prior experience. Price being unimportant and proximity/availability were not associated with education.

Multivariable models (Suppl. material 1) supported the bivariate patterns. Compared with respondents aged ≤ 30 years, those aged 31–40 years had higher odds of rating physician prescription as important/very important (aOR 1.89, 95% CI 1.21–2.95) and pharmacist recommendations as important/very important (aOR 1.72, 95% CI

Table 2. Factors influencing the purchase of OTC plant-based products (phytoproducts/phytopharmaceuticals).

Statement	1) Not important <i>n</i> (%)	2) Slightly important <i>n</i> (%)	3) Moderately important <i>n</i> (%)	4) Very important <i>n</i> (%)
I buy an herbal product for my child if prescribed by a physician.	182 (13.9)	179 (13.7)	498 (38.2)	446 (34.2)
I buy an herbal product for my child on a pharmacist's recommendation.	193 (14.8)	277 (21.2)	591 (45.3)	244 (18.7)
I buy an herbal product for my child based on previous experience.	180 (13.8)	180 (13.8)	442 (33.9)	503 (38.5)
I buy an herbal product because it is advertised.	678 (52.0)	345 (26.4)	193 (14.8)	89 (6.8)
Price is not important when purchasing an herbal product.	324 (24.1)	295 (21.9)	435 (32.3)	291 (21.7)
It is always available at a nearby pharmacy.	321 (24.8)	323 (24.9)	394 (30.4)	257 (19.7)
I buy herbal products because I consider them high quality, effective, and safe.	206 (15.8)	253 (19.4)	460 (35.2)	386 (29.6)

Table 3. Significant associations between decision factors and demographic variables (Pearson's χ^2 ; Cramér's *V*).

Demographic variable	Decision factor	df	<i>N</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i>	Cramér's <i>V</i>
Gender	Physician-prescribed	3	1305	8.566	0.036	0.081
Gender	Pharmacist recommendation	3	1305	10.938	0.012	0.092
Gender	Previous experience	3	1305	43.979	< 0.001	0.184
Gender	Advertising	3	1305	24.757	< 0.001	0.138
Gender	Price unimportant	3	1305	17.013	< 0.001	0.114
Gender	Availability nearby	3	1305	13.545	0.004	0.102
Gender	Perceived quality/safety	3	1305	30.802	< 0.001	0.154
Age group	Physician-prescribed	9	1305	24.781	0.003	0.080
Age group	Pharmacist recommendation	9	1305	33.282	< 0.001	0.092
Age group	Previous experience	9	1305	40.862	< 0.001	0.102
Age group	Price unimportant	9	1305	19.823	0.019	0.071
Age group	Advertising	9	1305	18.254	0.032	0.068
Age group	Perceived quality/safety	9	1305	38.061	< 0.001	0.099
Education	Physician-prescribed	12	1305	39.420	< 0.001	0.100
Education	Pharmacist recommendation	12	1305	31.154	0.002	0.089
Education	Previous experience	12	1305	100.007	< 0.001	0.160
Education	Advertising	12	1305	86.994	< 0.001	0.149
City	Physician-prescribed	12	1305	28.680	0.004	0.086
City	Pharmacist recommendation	12	1305	21.128	0.049	0.073
City	Previous experience	12	1305	77.538	< 0.001	0.141
City	Advertising	12	1305	106.865	< 0.001	0.165
City	Perceived quality/safety	12	1305	28.724	0.004	0.086

1.12–2.64). Respondents with secondary education (vs. bachelor's) had lower odds of assigning high importance to physician prescription (aOR 0.51, 95% CI 0.30–0.88) and previous experience (aOR 0.37, 95% CI 0.21–0.63). Male respondents were less likely to rate previous experience as important/very important (aOR 0.58, 95% CI 0.40–0.84). After adjustment, the city was not independently associated with higher importance ratings.

Purchasing channels further highlighted the central role of community pharmacies: 92.5% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they buy these products from a pharmacy, compared with 51.7% from a drugstore, 40.3% from an online pharmacy, and 21.6% from general internet sites. Perceptions of pharmacists were favorable: 76.9% agreed that they trust pharmacists' advice, 76.0% perceived pharmacists as willing to provide counseling, and 73.5% perceived pharmacists as accessible.

Discussion

The present study suggests that, within a large Bulgarian convenience sample, parents' decisions to purchase OTC plant-based products for children were driven primarily by prior experience and professionally endorsed advice. Previous experience and physician recommendation emerged as the strongest determinants, whereas advertising was clearly the weakest. This pattern aligns with international evidence indicating that caregiver self-medication decisions are usually anchored in familiarity, prior successful use, and trusted health information rather than in promotional messaging alone (Seth et al. 2023; Tarcuc et al. 2023; Haq et al. 2025). Taken together, these findings place the study within the broader literature on parental decision-making in pediatric self-care while preserving the limits of the design.

Pharmacists occupied a particularly important position in the decision architecture captured by this survey. Nearly two-thirds of respondents rated pharmacist recommendation as moderately or very important; most respondents reported favorable perceptions of pharmacists' accessibility, willingness to counsel, and trustworthiness; and community pharmacies were the dominant purchase channel. Taken together, these findings suggest that pharmacists are visible decision-shaping professionals in this setting whose communication may influence product selection, appropriateness of use, and referral behavior. From a practice perspective, this strengthens the rationale for structured pharmacist-led counseling for parents seeking plant-based OTC options for children and underscores the community pharmacy as the most actionable real-world intervention point in this pathway.

Another notable finding is the importance assigned to perceived product quality, effectiveness, and safety. This is plausible in a product segment in which plant-based options are often viewed as gentler, more natural, or more acceptable for children. Studies from other settings

likewise suggest that parental interest in such products is often linked to ideas of familiarity, tolerability, and perceived lower risk, although these perceptions do not automatically translate into equivalent evidence strength across products or indications (Petran et al. 2024; Aydın Aksoy et al. 2024). For that reason, community-pharmacy counseling remains important not only for access but also for expectation management: parents may need help distinguishing between plant origin, regulatory status, age appropriateness, and evidence-supported use. This extends the relevance of the findings beyond herbal-product use alone because similar tensions between perceived naturalness and evidence-aligned counseling recur across pediatric OTC care.

Although bivariate associations suggested differences across gender, age, education, and city, the adjusted models indicate that not every apparent demographic gradient remains independently explanatory after covariate control. The most policy- and practice-relevant signal is therefore not demographic fine-graining, but the broader pattern that parental choice in this sample was structured more by prior experience and trusted professional input than by advertising. That insight may be transferable to comparable OTC environments, especially those in which pharmacists occupy a visible gatekeeping and counseling role, although it should still be interpreted as practice-oriented evidence rather than as a population estimate. In that sense, the study offers a country-specific reference point for comparative work on parental self-medication behavior, community-pharmacy practice, and pediatric OTC use.

Future studies would benefit from probability-based sampling, qualitative interviews to explore decision pathways in greater depth, and analytical approaches that make fuller use of the ordinal structure of importance ratings, such as multivariable ordinal regression. Comparative work across countries would also be valuable because it could help distinguish broadly reproducible decision patterns from those that are more market- or system-specific and test whether the pharmacy-centered decision structure observed here recurs in other regulated OTC settings.

Limitations

The online survey design and convenience sampling approach may have introduced selection bias. Recruitment through parenting-focused digital channels likely favored respondents who were more digitally engaged and more willing to participate in child-health-related surveys. The marked predominance of female respondents, the concentration of responses from specific cities, and the relatively high educational profile of the sample further limit national representativeness. Because the study was cross-sectional, the observed associations should not be interpreted as causal. Finally, all outcomes were self-reported and are therefore subject to recall and social desirability bias.

Conclusion

Parents' decisions to purchase OTC plant-based products for children were driven predominantly by prior experience and professional healthcare advice, with advertising playing a distinctly smaller role. Pharmacists occupied a meaningful and actionable position within this decision process, while community pharmacies emerged as the main real-world purchase setting. These findings support a practical implication with immediate relevance to routine care: strengthening pharmacist-led OTC counseling may be one of the most feasible routes to safer, better-informed, and more evidence-aligned pediatric self-care with plant-based products. More broadly, the study offers a Bulgarian reference point for future research on parental decision-making, self-medication behavior, and community-pharmacy interventions in pediatric OTC care.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Participation was anonymous and voluntary. Before accessing the questionnaire, respondents received an information sheet describing the study purpose, confidentiality safeguards, and the right to withdraw and provided electronic informed consent.

The study involved an anonymous, voluntary online survey among adult participants and collected no directly identifying personal data. Under the local requirements applicable to this type of minimal-risk questionnaire study, formal ethics committee approval was not required.

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The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following: GPT.

Used for: Language, style and writing, Literature discovery and brainstorming.

The authors declare that artificial intelligence tools were used to assist with language editing, stylistic refinement, readability improvement, and preliminary literature-related brainstorming. All cited references, scientific interpretations, and final manuscript content were critically reviewed, verified, revised, and approved by the authors, who retain full responsibility for the final content.

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Author contributions

Bozhidarka Hadzhieva: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing—original draft. Milen Dimitrov: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing—review and editing, Supervision, Correspondence. Kristina Kilova: Investigation, Data curation, Resources, Project administration, Writing—review and editing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Supplementary material 1

Multivariable models

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Data type: docx

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